

PROJECT MANAGEMENT QUALITY: BEST PRACTICES AND SHORTCOMINGS

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Abstract: The organization of project management, practices implemented within the scope of the project, the importance and role of management in project management, the advantages and disadvantages of its practical application are considered. In connection with this thesis, ideas and proposals were developed in general on the implementation of start-up projects based on innovation and technology, the development of project management in a sharper way, the organization of projects of different levels.

Key words: Project, programs, project management, its advantages and disadvantages, Project environment, project cycle and stages

Introduction

Nowadays, we are living in the age of technology, that is, in the age where technology and technology are developed, it is possible to discover various news, new programs, electronic and online projects within countries, to create a unique project by gathering ideas and thoughts, to develop start-up projects. the exit is very developed. When we talk about the project in general, we can see big projects and programs that are very popular. Everyone may have a question. What is the project itself? What is the purpose of his duties? How to manage projects and why do we need them? Of course, scientists have different views and opinions on these questions. I would like to express my views on the purpose of the project and its types of tasks. The project question can be answered as follows. A project is a set of documents (calculations, drawings, models) prepared for the purpose of building a building, structure or creating a specific item. The project of a certain building or structure can be individually or in the same model. Currently, there are special and design institutes, departments and other creative associations that fulfill the orders of projects of various organizations. plan, goal, idea.

A project is a temporary enterprise designed to create unique products, services or results. The word project comes from the Latin verb proicere, "before action," which in turn comes from pro-, meaning priority (something that precedes something else in time (Greek prō), and iacere, "to do." Thus, " The word "project" originally meant "before an action". When the English language

first adopted this word, it referred to a plan for something, not to the act of carrying out that plan. What was done according to the project was known as an "object". has stages. Based on the project management institute, a project can be defined as a "temporary effort" aimed at bringing about change in teams, organizations, or societies. The result of a project is usually a new type of product, service, or outcome. (lack of proper ventilation) consists of specific and organized actions arising from a perceived opportunity. It seeks to implement a unique and innovative product, such as a product, service, process or, in some cases, scientific research. Every project has a beginning and an end. It is developed around the 4 points of project management: Plan, Processes, People and Power (eg scope of authority). It is bound by three constraints: calendar, cost, and quality. Each of them can be objectively defined and measured during the project life cycle. Some projects produce formal documents, output(s) and some impacts that may be positive or negative. Any project goes through several phases (stages). Of course, they must be managed in some way in order to carry out the project through all the phases (stages). In this sense, he managed famous projects such as the construction of the Egyptian pyramid or the Great Wall of China. Managed - not unsuccessful (we evaluate success only by timely completion or technical results) - projects in defense, fuel and energy and other sectors of the former Soviet Union were also managed. In the 1950s, developed G with a market economy In Arab countries, there is a need for an independent discipline such as "Project Management". This is due to the fact that the concept of project success is defined primarily by matching the final costs with the amount of allocated funds, savings and profit margins. The last one, in turn, depended on the complexity (systematic) of solving a number of tasks that make up the subject of management. In the late 1950s, one of the first methods of project management was the development of project planning and control methods (CPM and PERT methods). Initially, they used it to build the Atlas missile program and a large synthetic fiber factory. In the mid-1960s, these methods were actively studied and, to a lesser extent, began to be introduced into the capital construction practice of the USSR. It should be noted that at the end of the 1930s, Soviet scientists developed theoretical foundations and practical methods of calendar planning and flow construction using Gantt charts and cycle charts. and this, in many ways, is the foundation of the project management apparatus created later. In the 1970s, many large companies in the West began to develop and implement project management methods to respond

to the expansion and complexity of their operations in the face of intense competition.

Acceleration of this process was ensured by wide introduction of computer information processing systems. "E-Government and Digital Economy Project Management Center" DUK E-Government and Digital Economy Project Management Center under the National Agency of Project Management under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan 0 Pursuant to the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-:5624 of January 10, 2019 established. Areas of activity of the center: development of the "Electronic government" system and implementation of projects in the field of information and communication technologies (hereinafter referred to as projects) within the framework of the implementation of the "Digital Uzbekistan - 2030" program (hereinafter referred to as programs) future strategic directions of the programs, development of a unified approach, mechanisms and stages; Quality management in project management focuses on achieving long-term success by involving members of the organization at all levels to create the best products to meet customer needs. there is. Project quality management focuses on solving quality problems associated with projects so that all work meets established quality standards. It is useful to understand how quality management works to improve project success. Project objectives define the target status at the end of the project, the achievement of which is considered necessary to achieve the planned benefits. These can be formulated as SMART criteria: Projects are often managed by a steering group.

- ✓ Special
- ✓ Measurable (or at least quantifiable) achievement
- ✓ Available (Recently Agreed or Accepted)
- ✓ Actual (taking into account the current state of organizational resources)
- ✓ Time (limited)

Evaluation (measurement) is done at project closure. However, the progress of the project should be continuously monitored through monitoring and evaluation. Project quality management is a process that determines how the project intends to achieve the level of quality required for the overall success of the project. Project managers use this process to measure and evaluate the overall quality of the work and the processes involved to ensure that the project meets the desired quality standards. Teams usually establish these standards before the project begins to create measures for milestones and deliverables. This approach allows project managers to adjust parts of the project to meet

quality requirements if they do not meet objectives. The main objective of quality management is to ensure that the project and its results meet the needs of the client, company or end user. To do this, project managers strive to overcome various challenges, from time constraints to budget constraints. Quality management helps provide accurate measurements of progress to determine whether the project and its processes are meeting the standards required for success. There are several benefits associated with project quality assurance that contribute to project success and outcomes. Some of the main advantages are:

Improved customer satisfaction: One of the biggest benefits associated with quality management is increased customer satisfaction. If a product or service reaches customers and it is of poor quality, it will reflect badly on the company and reduce customer satisfaction. Thus, delivering high-quality products and services is an important factor in customer satisfaction, ensuring that customers enjoy what they receive. Quality project management ensures that project processes meet quality standards, which helps increase customer satisfaction.

High-quality products and services: One of the main objectives of quality management is to ensure that products effectively meet quality standards. By implementing quality management from the beginning of the project, the quality of the final product or service is improved. The processes and procedures put in place to improve project quality will help future projects as successful practices remain in a consistent workflow.

Naturally, we need special tools and IT systems like Projecto to keep everything (projects, tasks, jobs, etc.) under control. Project management methods are used not only in traditional fields such as large complex projects, construction and engineering, design-based production, highly competitive, high-tech production, but also in almost all fields for the development of enterprise activity and management of creative projects in the mass market. mass media, political and social projects. The project management process forms a direct and inverse relationship between subjects and management objects. directed enterprises are also the stages of the project cycle. As a result of the final review of the tasks of the main participants of the project, the important role of the Bank, which is one of the main investors providing financing for the project, is noted. It is very important. This organization helps in effective and honest analysis, evaluation and implementation of projects by experts in their profession. At the same time, the Fund for Reconstruction and Development, as one of the important organizers of financing is considered

In my opinion, the difference between a program and a project is that it is larger in scope and can consist of many projects. For example, the US government has a space program that includes several projects, such as the Challenger project. A construction company concludes a contract for the construction of an industrial technology park - a program consisting of several separate projects. The difference between a project and a production system is that a project is a one-time, non-periodic activity. Serial production, on the other hand, does not have a predetermined completion time and depends only on the availability and size of demand. When the demand disappears, the production cycle ends. Purely, production cycles are not projects.

Project quality management is not a stand-alone or distinct procedure that evaluates the level of output quality at the end of an activity. Instead, it is an ongoing process that begins and ends with the project. Every stage of the project management process, from the beginning through the project's closure phase, includes it. The goal of quality management is to increase stake holder satisfaction through ongoing process improvements that involve eliminating pointless steps. Making decisions and fixing problems fall into the same group. A best practice for benchmarking must demonstrate that it can produce high-quality project management outcomes quickly and effectively. Quality management in projects is one of the most important areas of ensuring the effective achievement of project objectives.

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